

Impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on PG Students of Central University of Punjab

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to explore the impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on PG students of Central University of Punjab. The objectives of the study were to analyze the level of usage of social networking sites and comparing the usage of SNS between male, female, science and humanities PG students of Central University of Punjab. The total number of 200 students were selected by using stratified random sampling technique for the collection of data. Data were collected by using self-made questionnaire. The study found that the maximum number of PG Students of Central University of Punjab comes under moderate level of usage of Social Networking Sites. It was also revealed that there is no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of science and humanities streams. Furthermore there is no significant difference between usage of Social Networking Sites among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Keywords: Social Networking Sites, Virtual Private Networks, PG Students, Central University of Punjab

Introduction

The 21st century is the world of technology where most people do not even imagine their life without technology. Modern communication technology has undoubtedly transformed the whole world into a “global community”. It helps people learn better, have an open mind and stay informed with global growth. Technology reveals to humanity a better way of doing things. For e.g beginning the day with the alarm on the phone and ends with the application messages on the smartphone. The use of technology in the classroom has also two sides both positive and negative. Most schools place more emphasis on computer education and the use of mobile learning as the use of this technology in today’s classroom helps students to participate and learn actively to the needs of the students and receive feedback from an expert teacher. But also many schools do not allow their students to use mobile devices because they think that by using this type of technology, students become technology-dependent and take less participation in face-to-face interaction with parents, teachers and colleagues who play a crucial role in improving social skills. Bandura in his social learning theory gives primary importance to observation. According to Bandura’s theory, children learn by observing their classmates, teachers and parents. Bandura emphasizes on social skills that can be acquired by interacting with society in today’s age. We discover that young students always interact with their technological toys, even most of the traffic accident is due to the use of the mobile phone during their journey.

Social Networking Sites

Social networking sites refer to various applications, websites or new online media that allows large numbers of individuals to share their information and develop a proper social and specialized contact. The various social networking sites are Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, snapshot, Youtube etc. Social networking sites (SNS) are online services that emphasize the creation of a connection between people to enable them to share their interests. These network sites allow people to share their information. Therefore, the main purpose of social networking sites is to allow people to share their real-life interests, activities and experiences.

Social networks refer mainly to the means used for interaction, which have become phenomena of growth in the social and academic field. Social media allows people and organizations to create, participate and share new or existing content through multi-way communication. Commonly, the phrase "social network sites" is used as a general term for all social networks, including Facebook, Twitter and Myspace.

Social networks have become a very important part of our personal and professional life. In a day we dedicate quite a few hours of our time to social networks, commenting, publishing, etc. Social networks are spreading the product of various popular social networking platforms. Today, social networking sites are widely used by millions of people. The web provides a means to search for information. Many people have discovered that the Internet can be used to connect with many other people, either for commercial or commercial reasons, to make new friends or to awaken old friends and relatives long lost some time ago. SNS is web-based services that, within a limited system, allow individuals the creation of a semi-profile and a complete list of new users with which they share their views, associations and points of view. Social networking websites contain over 100,000,000 registered users. Most of the users of SNS are young, which have been called 'Digital Citizens'.

The growth of social networks over the years has transformed the way many users experience the Internet. Gone are the days when the Internet was used as a one-way transmission system where users only downloaded data, information from a limited number of content providers. This sense of Internet use has changed the definition of social networks that is now described in terms of collaboration, coexistence and creativity. As pictures now the internet is certainly very different from that of 10 years before. Among all these technological developments, it has been thought that educators are expected to prepare themselves with the world of new social media applications and users of social networks that are mostly university students. The opportunities offered by social networks to collaborate, establish contacts, share knowledge and content is considered best for higher education studies. It is the reliable source for teachers to be in contact with their students in the campus. With the help of Social networks, teachers are able to share information with their students by creating groups. Therefore, it is important that higher level educators can approach social networks in a considered and objective way.

Over the past decade, every social networking application has worked collaboratively to provide a completely new multimedia experience that can now be accessed via mobile devices. In a related study, Brissette (2002) found that university students of both sexes completed measures of perceived stress, depression, network of friendship and social perception. Vitak (2008) reported in a study that there are several reasons why people use a social networking site. One of the reasons is that they meet strangers and become friends. Through social networking sites, users can keep their interpersonal relationship with their friends and can send private messages and use chat rooms as a method of communication. Lack et. al. (2009) reported in a study that most of the students who use social networking sites can easily access other user profiles by using their account information. He further says that formal education should be given over to students regarding the use of these sites. In a study, Brandtzaeg et. al. (2009) reported that peoples and college student's uses social networking sites by several motivational reasons. Moreover the study has made several attempts to understand the choice, use, dispersal, adoption and acceptance of social networking sites among university students. Banquil et. al. (2009) reported in a study that "Social networking sites negatively impact academic performance" and also indicated that friendship networks often require access to information and knowledge directly and indirectly and the effect of friendship on the academic performance of the students was confirmed. Social networking sites significantly influence the educational performance of university students. Bicen and Cavus (2010) reported in their study that the use and exchange of knowledge on the internet is an integral or internal part of the life of university students. The findings of the study also reveal that Live Spaces and Facebook are the sites commonly used by students. Miller et. al. (2010) conducted a survey among students on the use of social networking sites and the capability of published content. The answers indicate that students regularly publish inappropriate content for all types of audiences, especially for potential employers. Park (2010) reported in his study that students used the profile service more than the community service while graduates used the community service plus the profile service. However, most of the faculty members were not active users of social media. Students are very addicted to social media and prefer to use Facebook very much and are always in favour of using these technologies to promote work in the classroom than teachers. Teachers are more likely to use more "traditional" technologies such as e-mail. Das and Sahoo (2010) reported in their study that people use SNS for many purposes mainly because SNS offers the opportunity to express their points of view and provide independence and connect them with millions of people in the world. Kuppuswamy and Narayan (2010) reported the impact of social networking sites on the education of youth and found that social networking websites have both positive as well as negative impact on the education of youth, depending on their usage. Lin & Lu (2011) reported that enjoyment was the most influential factor for usage of growing social networking sites among college students. Hampton et. al. (2011) reported that social networks quickly gained popularity among their users and have now become an integral part of the lives of most of their users.

Rationale of the study

Social Networking Sites (SNS) have become a subject of importance. It marked the shift of producer-generated content towards user-generated content. In the context of technology-enhanced learning, this paradigm change marks the shift from class e-learning, based on courses and the sequential presentation of learning material, towards more active participation of the learners and the support of the learners as a community of interest. On the basis of reviews, the investigator found that Social Networking Sites are Web-based platforms on which individuals connect with other users to generate and maintain social connections. Some studies reveal that users use Social Networking Sites for enjoyment. But some reviews show that the use of SNSs may lead to addiction. On one hand, Social Networking Sites have the potential to prevent users from feeling lonely because they enable social interaction and allow users to reveal characteristics of their identity and express emotion that may be relevant to their life experience. But on the other hand, there are many opportunities for miscommunications and mismanaged expectations and maladaptive tendencies can be exaggerated, leaving individuals feeling in a greater sense of isolation. Central University of Punjab (CUPB) is a university where students from all over the country come for their future studies. Almost all the students of Central University of Punjab are using Social Networking Sites despite ban by the Universities authorities. Still students use Social Networking Sites by using Virtual Private Networks revealing the addiction of students towards Social Media. Hence the investigator got an opportunity to explore the impact of usage Social Networking Sites on the students of Central University of Punjab.

Objectives

- To study the level of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- To compare the usage of Social Networking Sites of male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.
- To compare the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab.

Hypotheses

The study under investigation has the following hypotheses:

- Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab will come under higher level of usage of Social Networking Sites
- There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.
- There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab.

Materials and Methods

In the present study, the researcher used the descriptive method of research. A sample of 200 postgraduate students was taken and then classified according to their flows. The sample consisted of 100 male and 100 female students. Techniques percentage analysis, t-test were used for testing the hypotheses. For the present study, the researcher used the stratified random sampling technique for the purpose of collection of data. Data were collected from the PG students of Central Punjab University, Bathinda. Hence all the PG students of Central University of Punjab constituted as the population of the study. For the present study, the investigator used the self-made questionnaire on checking the Usage of Social Networking Sites. The questionnaire had 17 Positive, 11 Negative and 6 Neutral statements. The items were selected keeping in view the modern trends in technology. The positive items were scored on 5 point scale starting with 5 as the highest score and 1 as the lowest score. However the negative items were scored with 1 mark as highest score and 5 as the lowest score. The neutral items were given 1 mark for each.

Result and Discussion

Table 1.1 reveals the level of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed that out of 200 students, 18% of the PG students fall under higher level of Usage of Social Networking Sites, 68% fall in the moderate level and 14% fall in the Low level of Usage of Social Networking Sites. It was found that majority of the PG students of Central University of Punjab have moderate level of Usage of Social Networking Sites. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.1: Level of Usage of Social Networking Sites

Usage of SNS	N	High Level of Usage of SNS	Moderate Level of Usage of SNS	Low Level of Usage of SNS
	200	18%	68%	14%

The below table 1.2 shows the Mean, S.D, t- value and level of significance of usage of Social Networking Sites among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab. From the table it was revealed that the mean value of Usage of social networking sites of male and female are 86.88 and 86.78 respectively. The S.D. of male students is 7.67 and that of female students is 5.96. Also, the calculated t-value is 0.10 which is less than table value of t with the df 198 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.98. Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference between usage of Social Networking Sites among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.2: Comparison of usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	't' value	Level of significance
Male	100	86.88	7.67	0.10	Not Significant
Female	100	86.78	5.96		

Table 1.3 shows the Mean, S.D, t- value and level of significance of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab. From the table, it was revealed that the mean value of Usage of social networking sites of Humanities and Science stream students are 87.56 and 86.1 respectively. The S.D. of Humanities student is 6.484 and that of Science students is 7.156. Also the calculated t-value is 1.50 which is less than table value of t with the df 198 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.98. Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference between usage of Social Networking Sites among science and Humanities PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.3: Comparison of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of CUPB

Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	df	't' value	Level of significance
Humanities	100	87.56	6.484	198	1.50	Not Significant
Science	100	86.1	7.156			

Major findings of the Study:

Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab comes under moderate level of usage of Social Networking Sites. The statistical data of the study reveal that 68% of the PG students of Central University of Punjab have moderate level of usage of Social Networking Sites. However, only 18% & 14% of the PG students comes under High & Low level of usage of social networking sites respectively. Despite the ban on social media Sites by the authorities in the University, the students are not addicted towards Social Media. The male and female PG students of the University have equal level of usage of Social Media websites. Although the enrolment number of the University is high with respect to female students. Still the usage of these websites has no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites. The statistical data reveal that not only male and female students but the students belonging to Humanities and Science streams have the same level of usage of Social Networking Sites.

Conclusion

Social Networking Sites have become part and parcel of our lives. With an increasing number of people, especially teenagers, who use the Internet to socialize with friends, connect with appropriate people or even use it as a place to express their feelings, SNS have become a tool for problems like addiction. They are playing an important and significant role in making decisions on the occasions of universal civilization in an economic, political, social and educational way. The students surfing the social media needs to be monitored about their usage. Despite the Universities are banning the surfing of these websites in their campuses still there is a need to ban the third party software's which help students to access these websites. The investigator of the study is fully aware of the limitations under which the present research was conducted and therefore accepts that no broad conclusions could be made. These findings are only indicative of trends and hence following suggestions can be given for further research. The tool adopted for the present study was used as such without any modifications. The results of the study lack in external validity as the sample size was not large. The study was limited to post graduate students of Central University of Punjab.

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